

Transparency and Accountability in Public Administration

Dr. Ram Sagar Pandit

A Research Scholar, An Associate Professor (T.U.)

Email: ramsagar526835@gmail.com

Abstract

This study analyses the transparency and accountability in public administration with the theme of this conference. Madhesh Province wants to make a better Madhesh. For better Madhesh, public administration must be worked in correct way. Transparency and accountability are the two wheels for better administration. Where, there is no such mechanism of administration that can not provide proper administration for people. This research paper takes clear objectives to analyse the findings to show the mechanism and find out the research theme. Methodology is must to achieve the goal of this paper. Transparency in public administration involves open sharing of government information and activities, allowing citizens to see how public resources are managed and decisions are made ? Accountability is the obligation of public officials to be answerable for their actions and use of resources, reporting on outcomes and accepting consequence for failures. Together, both are foundational to good governance, building public trust, reducing corruptions and ensuring that public administration is efficient, effective and responsive to citizens needs. They are interrelated with one another. Transparency enables accountability and accountability fosters transparency. Mechanism for implementation is as procurement and financial management, information disclosure, codes of conduct, complaint and grievance system, and sanctions. These mechanisms are needed for successful public administration recommendation suggests do. For better administration, corruption should be reduced, increased public trust, improved governance, enhanced legitimacy and citizen engagement. Our provincial government wants to provide a better services for its people. Government should be alert to control corruptions and use code of conducts strictly from minister to officials. Overall, this research contributes to a more comprehensive understanding of transparency and accountability in public administration of Nepal. Advocating for policy frameworks that promote policy a good governance for easy service to the people.

Keywords: transparency, accountability, public administration, mechanism, good governance, answerable, foundational